

**Reversed-phase High Performance Liquid
Chromatographic Determination of Ibuprofen
and Ethambutol in Pharmaceutical
Dosage Form**

A. K. SEN

Central Public Health and Drugs Laboratory (Drug Wing),
Calcutta-700 015

A. BANDYOPADHYAY, G. PODDER and B. CHOWDHURY*

School of Tropical Medicine, Calcutta-700 073

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IBUPROFEN, 2-(4-isobutylphenyl)propionic acid, is an anti-inflammatory agent used in the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis and osteoarthritis¹. Ethambutol hydrochloride, chemically, (RR)-N,N'-bis(1-hydroxymethylpropyl)ethylenediamine is an excellent antituberculous agent². The only official method for the analysis of the former drug is acid-base titration³, while that for the latter is a non-aqueous titration⁴. Both these methods are time-consuming, requiring extraction for 5-6 times for fairly good results and thereby increase the probability of personal error. The spectrophotometric method⁵ for the analysis of ethambutol hydrochloride reported by the authors also suffers disadvantages. It was therefore of interest to develop simple and convenient method for the determination of these two drugs. This communication describes a simple and direct isocratic hplc process for the determination of both these drugs when each of them is present in single pharmaceutical formulation using analgin as the internal standard. The method is also effective for the determination of percentage purity of the pharmaceutical grade raw materials of these drugs.

Experimental

A Water Associates' liquid chromatograph equipped with a 510 dual reciprocating solvent pump, a U 6K universal injector, a 440 UV absorbance detector and a SE 120 single pen recorder was used. The chromatograph contained a Water Associate's stainless steel μ Bondapak C₁₈ column (300 × 3.9 mm i.d.) packed with octadecyl silane chemically bonded to porous silica (10 μ m). The entire experiment was carried out at an ambient temperature of 20° using methanol-water (70 : 30) as the mobile phase under isocratic condition at a flow-rate of 1 ml min⁻¹ and a record chart speed of 10 mm min⁻¹. The uv detector was set at 254 nm (1.0 aufs).

Methanol (hplc grade ; Mallinckrodt, USA) and water (hplc grade, Spectrochem) were used.

A solution of standard analgin (1 mg ml⁻¹) in methanol was prepared as internal standard. A set of ten standard solutions for each of ibuprofen and ethambutol hydrochloride (containing 1.0-0.1 mg

ml⁻¹) in methanol were prepared. The solutions were filtered through Millipore filter paper (0.45 μ m) to remove any impurity of larger diameter which might affect the column and consequently the results. The solutions were then stored in air-tight flasks at 20°.

Preparation of samples for hplc analysis : Ibuprofen and ethambutol hydrochloride tablets were accurately weighed and the procedure of working standard preparation was followed for preparing the sample solutions.

An aliquot (10 μ l) of each of the standard and sample preparations was injected into the chromatograph. The representative chromatograms are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The retention times

Fig. 1. The chromatogram : (1) analgin (i.s) and (2) ethambutol hydrochloride.

Fig. 2. The chromatogram : (1) analgin (i.s) and (3) ibuprofen.

for ibuprofen and ethambutol hydrochloride were 90 and 100s respectively and that for analgin (the internal standard) was 42s. The amounts of ibuprofen and ethambutol hydrochloride in the solid dosage forms were calculated using the following formula,

$$\% \text{ of the drug} = \frac{A_u}{A_s} \frac{c}{m} \times 100$$

where A_u is the area of sample peak, A_s the area of standard peak, c the concentration of standard and m the mass of the drug in the sample (according to the label claim).

The ratios of peak heights of ibuprofen to that of internal standard against the amount of ibuprofen were linear over the range 1.0–50.0 μg . Linear calibration curve was also obtained with ethambutol hydrochloride upto 50 μg of the drug.

Results and Discussion

The method was successfully applied for the determination of ibuprofen and ethambutol hydrochloride in three different formulations for each of the drugs by comparison with the standard calibration curves and the results were checked with the official^{3,4} methods (Table 1). The reproducibility of the hplc analysis was highly satisfactory and the standard deviation and the coefficient of variation ($n=10$) for ethambutol hydrochloride were only

1.82 and 0.252, and those for ibuprofen were only 1.61 and 0.432 respectively.

The present method is advantageous due to the fact that it is a direct isocratic method and requires no separation of the drug from other active ingredients. Moreover, it does not require any derivatization also. Hplc, therefore, provides a simple and rapid method for the determination of ibuprofen and ethambutol hydrochloride. The method can easily be applied for the routine analysis of these drugs. The present technique may be extended for the determination of ibuprofen and ethambutol in biological materials.

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TABLE 1—RESULTS OF COMMERCIAL TABLETS CONTAINING IBUPROFEN/ETHAMBUTOL BY OFFICIAL AND PRESENT METHODS

Drug	Sample no.	Label claim (mg/tablet)	Found (mg)	
			Official method	Present method*
Ibuprofen	1	200	197.2	198.4
	2	200	198.4	197.3
	3	200	196.5	196.4
	4	400	395.6	394.8
	5	400	396.3	397.4
Ethambutol hydrochloride	1	200	194.27	196.4
	2	200	198.08	197.5
	3	400	398.04	399.5

*Average of five replicate determinations.

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